

**THE PRINCIPLE OF CONFIDENTIALITY IN INTERNATIONAL
COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION**

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ANNOTATION

This article examines such a distinctive feature of international commercial arbitration as confidentiality. The author cites recognized aspects of confidentiality and discusses the grounds for confidentiality of proceedings. Analyzing national legislation and regulations of arbitration institutions, the author expresses an opinion on a possible transition to the principle of transparency of arbitration proceedings.

Key words: international commercial arbitration, confidentiality, privacy, disclosure, information.

**ПРИНЦИП КОНФИДЕНЦИАЛЬНОСТИ В МЕЖДУНАРОДНОМ
КОММЕРЧЕСКОМ АРБИТРАЖЕ**

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Аннотация

ILM – FAN TA’LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

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В данной статье рассматривается такая отличительная черта международного коммерческого арбитража как конфиденциальность. Автор приводит признанные аспекты конфиденциальности и рассматривает основания конфиденциальности разбирательства. Анализируя национальное законодательство и регламенты арбитражных институтов, автором выражается мнение о возможном переходе к принципу прозрачности арбитражного разбирательства.

Ключевые слова: международный коммерческий арбитраж, конфиденциальность, приватность, раскрытие, информация.

A basic principle of the state justice system is that trials must be conducted in public. The principle of publicity of justice is enshrined in paragraph 1 of Art. 6 of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms 1950: “Everyone, in the event of a dispute concerning his civil rights and obligations ... has the right to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal established by law”¹. International commercial arbitration (hereinafter referred to as “ICA”, “arbitration”), on the

¹ Конвенция о защите прав человека и основных свобод (Заключена в Риме 4 ноября 1950 г.) // Доступ из СПС «КонсультантПлюс».

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contrary, is characterized by confidentiality. It is recognized as one of the main advantages and basic principle of ICA. In international judicial and arbitration practice, such aspects of confidentiality are distinguished as 1) the closed or “private” nature of hearings; 2) confidentiality of documents and information; 3) confidentiality of information about the proceedings; 4) confidentiality of the arbitration award, including a ban on publication of the award without the consent of the parties². Let us consider in more detail the second and fourth aspects, namely maintaining the confidentiality of documents and information submitted by the parties to arbitration and the confidentiality of the decision itself.

It is worth noting separately that a number of authors propose to distinguish between the concepts of “privacy” and “confidentiality” of arbitration, narrowing the understanding of the latter to the aspect considered in this article³. However, let’s take this discussion beyond the scope of this work and understand the word “confidentiality” to mean both phenomena.

For a long time, confidentiality was an implied principle of the ICA and was not enshrined in legislation. it was concluded that the parties expressed their will to

² Комментарий к Федеральному закону «Об арбитраже (третейском разбирательстве) в Российской Федерации»: постатейный, научно-практический; под ред. О.Ю. Скворцова, М.Ю. Савранского. М.: Статут, 2016. // Доступ из СПС «КонсультантПлюс».

³ Лашков Н.С. Конфиденциальность арбитражного разбирательства. Понятие и пределы // Закон. 2015. № 10. С. 48–58; Ерофеева Н.М. Приватность и конфиденциальность в международном коммерческом арбитраже // Гуманитарные, социально-экономические и общественные науки. 2015. №10 С. 186-187.

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submit the dispute in favor of arbitration of a private nature. Consequently, they thereby abandoned public trial in favor of confidentiality.

Currently, the legal basis for the application of confidentiality clauses may be: 1) national law, 2) institutional arbitration rules, 3) an arbitration clause or confidentiality agreement, and 4) judicial practice (which confirms the implied nature of the confidentiality clause). Sources of confidentiality of arbitration proceedings can complement and clarify each other.

For example, in the Hong Kong Arbitration Law in section. 18 states: “unless the parties agree otherwise, neither party has the right to publish, disclose or transmit information relating to the arbitration proceedings or the arbitral award made within the framework of the process”⁴. In this case, the parties have the right to enter into a confidentiality agreement, which provides for the desired level of confidentiality, namely, means of ensuring or a list of information that, under certain circumstances, may be made public.

The presumption of confidentiality at the legislative level is rather an exception to the rule. Basically, national legislation on MCA follows two paths: (i)

⁴ Arbitration Ordinance, Cap. 609: URL: <https://www.elegislation.gov.hk/hk/cap609> (дата обращения 20.09.2019) (цит. по Международный коммерческий арбитраж: Учебник ; выпуск 9 ; 2-е изд., перераб. И доп.; отв. ред. Т.А. Лунаева ; науч. ред. О.Ю. Скворцов, М.Ю. Савранский, Г.В. Севастьянов. М.: Статут, 2018).

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either deliberately moves away from direct regulation of this issue⁵, giving the parties the opportunity, if they wish, to establish in the agreement the obligation to maintain the confidentiality of information that has become known to the parties in during the arbitration, (ii) or establishes a rule of confidentiality only for domestic arbitration disputes. The first path is the most popular, largely due to the fact that most countries have adopted the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration, which does not regulate this issue in detail⁶. The second path was taken by legislators in France and Russia after reforms were carried out in both countries. According to Art. 1464 (4) of the French New Code of Civil Procedure, domestic arbitration is confidential unless the parties agree to the contrary. Similar regulation is provided for in Art. 21 of the Federal Law of December 29, 2015 No. 382-FZ “On Arbitration (Arbitration Proceedings) in the Russian Federation”, but confidentiality can also be limited by federal law.

Another significant limitation on confidentiality is the procedure for recognition and enforcement of ICA decisions in state court. The literature notes that the confidentiality of the decision is in the hands of the parties as long as the parties comply with the arbitration decision, by their own behavior and voluntary execution of the decision they maintain the secrecy of their relations and appeal to

⁵ Например, в Англии см. Английский Арбитражный акт (Arbitration Act) 1996 г.; в Швейцарии гл. 12 Закона «О международном частном праве» 1987 г.

⁶ Smeureanu I.M. Confidentiality in International Commercial Arbitration. Kluwer Law International, 2011. P. 21.

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arbitration⁵⁹. In rare cases, the courts accommodate the parties halfway, providing the opportunity to challenge the decision behind closed doors⁶⁰. As a rule, the parties are denied a closed hearing⁷.

Confidentiality of arbitration proceedings can hardly be called a principle of the ICA due to the ambiguity of the approaches of states and arbitration institutions to this legal institution. Parties who have confidentiality needs to conceal sensitive or valuable information should take their own precautions by including a confidentiality clause in the arbitration clause.

The opinion is increasingly expressed in the scientific literature that the principle of confidentiality in the ICA will replace the principle of transparency. This trend is evidenced by the UNCITRAL Rules on Transparency in Treaty-Based Investor-State Arbitration, which entered into force in 2014⁸. The implementation of the Transparency Rules will essentially make the investment arbitration process public. Also one cannot ignore the fact that more and more institutional arbitrations are moving towards the practice of publishing arbitral awards, having previously edited the text in such a way as to prevent identification of the dispute or the parties.

⁷ Определение АС г. Москвы от 09.07.2015 по делу № А40-66296/2015; Постановление Третьего арбитражного апелляционного суда от 20 марта 2015 г. по делу № А33-21695/2014 // Доступ из СПС «КонсультантПлюс».

⁸ Правила о прозрачности в контексте арбитражных разбирательств между инвесторами и государствами на основе международных договоров. URL: <https://uncitral.un.org/sites/uncitral.un.org/files/mediadocuments/uncitral/ru/rules-on-transparency-r.pdf> (дата обращения: 20.09.2019).

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It is perhaps not unreasonable that the arbitration community speaks only about the confidentiality of arbitration proceedings, because confidentiality as a general rule ceases to exist.

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